

4TU.ResearchData: A repository service for FAIR data

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Research Data Management Planning

Young Water Professionals Regional Conference

BeNeLux 2022

 4TU.ResearchData
SCIENCE • ENGINEERING • DESIGN

Today's aim:

To inform you about 4TU.ResearchData and its services to support researchers in creating and reusing FAIR data

- **What is 4TU.ResearchData**
 - The organisation
 - The repository
- **Our services**
 - Training
 - Consultancy
- **The community**
 - Our members
 - FAIR data initiatives

What is 4TU.ResearchData?

- International data repository
<https://data.4tu.nl/portal>
- Available to researchers globally
- Founded in 2010

Science

Engineering

Design

Sharing

Curation

Access

Preservation

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

4TU.Federation

Select an account to login to Figshare and 4TU.ResearchData

 If your institution is not listed, [eduID \(NL\)](#) is available as an alternative.

 Academisch Medisch Centrum (AMC)

 Delft University of Technology

 Deltares

 Driestar educatief

 eduID (NL)

No eduID? [Request one!](#)

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to continue to [Figshare](#) and [4TU.ResearchData](#)

Stay logged in

[Email a magic link](#)

Other sign-in options

[Sign in with a security key](#) or [type a password](#).

Deposits are assigned a DOI for linking and findability

Data publication and citation increases impact and visibility

Restricted access and embargo for confidential data

Personal service of metadata and data review (tick box, QC)

Need help?

GitHub/GitLab integration for publishing versions of code

F_{indable} A_{ccessible} I_{nteroperable} R_{eusable}

Source: Wikimedia

Usage-statistics: Views, Downloads Citations

Trusted, safe and secure, long-term preservation of research data

We support a variety of technical science disciplines

Mathematics

Physics

Chemistry

Earth Sciences

Atmospheric Sciences

Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience

Geomatic Engineering

Environmental Sciences

Biology

Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences

Information and Computing Sciences

Nanotechnology

Aerospace Engineering

Civil Engineering

Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Built Environment and Design

Materials Engineering

Mechanical Engineering

Medical and Health Sciences

Business and Management

- Atmospheric science (3321 datasets)
- Geomatic engineering (3213 datasets)
- Climate change (3211 datasets)

Our services

- 1TB data/user/year free
- Dedicated support for uploading data/code (NetCDF/OPeNDAP)
<https://data.4tu.nl/info/en/about-your-data/netcdf-and-opendap>

- Access to the Carpentries (data and software)
- Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL)
- Disciplinary workshops (e.g. materials science)
<https://community.data.4tu.nl/category/training-events/>

- Policy and service development
- Bespoke workshops and training
- Collaborative funding proposals

What is the goal of our community?

TU/e

Our community aims to provide an inclusive space for researchers and data supporters to connect and exchange knowledge about the best practices for creating and reusing FAIR data.

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/>

What does the community do together?

Communications
(website, Slack,
newsletter)

Working and
focus groups

FAIR data promotion
(Twitter, LinkedIn)

Researcher stories,
Recognition & reward

Community calls,
Networking events

Disciplinary training
and workshops

FAIR Data Fund
€3.500/application

Internship
programme

Thank you for your attention!

Quick links:

[Information website](#)

[Data portal](#)

[Community platform](#)

[Subscribe to mailing list](#)

[Highlights 2020](#)

[Slack workspace](#)

Contact

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